

How to cite: ThankGod et al, (2025): Dividend Policy and Financial performance of Selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *Scholarly J. Bus. Admin.* 12(2) 134-147
<https://zenodo.org/uploads/15422407>

Scholarly Journal of Business Administration: ISSN 2276-7126 © 2025 Scholarly-Journals (Online) & Open Access

Vol olume-12 | Issue-2 | February 2025

Dividend Policy and Financial performance of Selected Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis

ThankGod, Ubulom (DBA in view); Mgbataogu, Ifeanyi (PhD) & Okocha, Aleruchi (PhD)

University of Port Harcourt Business School,
Department of Finance and Banking, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt.

Received 23 December, 2024, Accepted 13 January, 2025, Published 22 February, 2025

Following the agelong controversy on the relevance of dividend policy to financial performance of corporate firms, this study investigates the nature of relationship and the effect of dividend policy on the financial performance of selected quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2011-2022. Utilizing time series data sourced from the annual reports of the quoted banking firms and thus given a total observation of 60, dividend payout ratio, dividend yield and earnings retention ratio were employed as indices of dividend policy, while market price per share utilized as proxy of market value. The study employed ex-post facto research design. The panel fixed effect regression technique was carried out to reveal the short run relationship at the 95% confidence interval. From the findings of the study, dividend payout ratio and dividend yield have positive and significant influence on market price per share; whereas, earnings retention ratio though negatively related also has significant effect on market price per share of the selected quoted banking firms in Nigeria. In conclusion, the dividend policy adopted by the select quoted banking firms significantly determines their market value and by extension the financial performance. The study recommends among others that Board of directors of quoted deposit money banks should declare dividends out of the earnings, no matter how little, as doing so will lead to increase in share price. Again, the banking firms should adopt a policy of high dividend payout ratio in order to attract increase in stock price.

Key words: Dividend policy, financial performance, Panel data, Fixed effects, Deposit Money Banks

INTRODUCTION

In finance and economics literature, the relevance or otherwise of dividend policy is one of the most controversial issues. Black (1976) argues that “the harder we look at the dividend picture, the more it seems like a puzzle, with pieces that just do not fit together”. This mystery led to the emergence of a handful of competing theoretical and empirical research to explain why companies pay or do not pay dividends. After decades of non-stop research, dividend policy is still listed as one of the top ten crucial unresolved issues in the world of finance in which no consensus has been reached (Brealey & Myers, 2003). Several theories have been

proposed to ascertain whether there is a relationship between dividend policy and firm value (including financial performance), but there has not been any consensus to this. Miller and Modigliani (1961) for instance objected to the relevance of dividend policy, and thus, concluded that it does not affect firm value or financial performance. A study by Amidu and Abor (2006) shows that dividend policy influences firm performance measured by its profitability. The results showed a positive and significant relationship between return on assets, return on equity, growth in sales and dividend policy. Howatt (2009) also stated that positive changes in dividends with positive future changes in earnings per share.

However, Lie (2005) argues that there is limited evidence that firms that pay dividend experience

*Corresponding author email: thankgodubulom@gmail.com

successive performance improvements. Haven reported by Arumah (2012) that some banks quoted in the Nigeria Stock Exchange have failed to meet the requirement of paying dividend on a yearly basis for a number of years, and also considering the fact that based on the statutory requirement of Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA, 1990) as amended, payment of dividend should be on the basis of net profit for the period. The questions are; is it that the financial status of these organizations did not favour the payment of dividend during these periods? Is there any relationship existing between the financial performance and the dividend policies made by banks in Nigeria.

Most studies carried out on the topic were conducted in developed economies and the result may therefore not address the peculiarities in emerging/developing economies. It is suggested that corporate finance models are developed with assumptions that are consistent with developed countries, which causes these models to fail when tested in emerging ones (Bekaert & Harvey, 2018). In the same line, Lagoarde-Segot (2020) contends that managerial models are developed in Western countries, which make them poor guides to business decisions when applied in a different institutional context. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, the limited studies carried out in the emerging/developing economies include Aivazian, Booth and Cleary (2003), Ajanthan (2013), Ali (2007), Amidu (2007), Asamoah (2010) Jabbouri (2016), Kazmierska-Jozwiak (2015) and Lagoarde-Segot (2013). Studies conducted in Nigeria include Adelegan (2002, 2003), Adelegan and Inanga (2001), Izedonmi and Eriki (2006), Musa (2009), Nnadi and Akomi (2008), Nnadi, Wogboroma and Kabel (2013), Nwosu (2008), Odedokun(1995), Odesa and Ekezie (2015), Oyejide (1976), Rufus and Soyoye (2014) and Soyode (1975). The findings of most studies in Nigeria tend to be similar with regards to dividend policy of Nigeria firms.

Further, investors' perception of the performance of a corporate organization is a topical issue in corporate finance (Akinola & Akinsulere, 2019). Thus, recognizing that investment decision made by investors is a crucial issue that affects value of listed companies, this study seeks to ascertain how corporate dividend policy is perceived by investors. Again, in modern finance, it is proven that shareholder wealth maximization is superior goal of the firm, the question arises also how dividend policy of the firm affect this cardinal objective. It is in consideration of these that this study sets out to evaluate how dividend policy affects the financial performance of select quoted banking firms in Nigeria for the period between 2011 and 2022.

Theoretical Framework and Empirical Literature Review

There are a number of theories in Finance and

Economics literature arguing for both relevance and irrelevance of dividend policy in influencing the financial performance of corporate firms. These theories were methodically explained in Nwude (2020) and Yegon., Cheruiyot, Sang, Cheruiyot, Kirui and Rotich (2014). However, the study is underpinned by the theories explained below:

Bird-In-The-Hand Theory

Linter (1962) and Gordon (1963) outlines that dividends are relevant in establishing the value of an organization. The main concept is that investor or shareholders avoid risk and favour current dividends owing to their reduced level of risk in comparison to future possible capital gains. Capital gains refer to possible future income investors may earn from sale of their shares hence investors prefer dividend due to the high risk associated with capital gains. Consequently, sure dividend income is more desirable than two birds in the bush that is, uncertain capital gains (Mutwiri, 2014). Investors will always favour dividends because of time value of money (Munyua, 2014). Based on this theory, dividend payments can then be linked with growth in firm's value (Al-Malkawi, Raffert & Pillai, 2010). This therefore implies that a rise in the dividend pay-out of a firm, results in a rise in share price. Consequently, a higher dividend payout ratio leads to maximization of a firm's value (Aduda & Kimathi, 2011).

Information Signaling Effect Theory

This theory was made popular by (Ross, 1977) he asserted that dividend policy can be used as an important signal in an inefficient market to predict future expectation about the market. For example, if management decide to pay high dividend for a given period these can serve as a signal to the market, of high profit, in the future to ensure the high payout continues. This signal process causes the market forces of demand and supply to increase the value of the firm. Similarly, in another study conducted by (Pettit, 1972) he suggested that dividend paid to shareholder have huge information value about the prediction of the firm. This is because there is an assumption that the manager will only raise their dividend only when they are sure that the earning has externally increased.

Agency theory

This theory suggests that dividend policy has huge influence on agency cost. It usually arises as a result of distinction between owners and those involved in the day today control of the organization. According to a study conducted by (DeAngelo et al, 2006) reducing free cash flow in an organization will go a long way to reduce the agency problem in quoted companies. He further emphasized that, this agency problem is common in

some companies because a manager will not always want to adopt the dividend policy that will ensure the wealth of the shareholder is maximized but will rather choose dividend policy that will increase their own control in the organization is maintained.

Empirical Review

Empirical literature is with controversy over dividend payout policy and retention as it affects firms' performance and its value by researchers. The earliest major attempt to explain dividend behavior of companies has been credited to John Lintner in 1956 who conducted his study on American companies in the middle of 1950s. Since then, there has been an ongoing debate on dividend policy in the developed and developing countries.

These issues did not receive any serious attention among academic scholars in Nigeria until 1974 when Uzoaga and Alozieuwa attempted to highlight the pattern of dividend policy pursued by Nigerian firms particularly since and during the period of indigenization and participation programme defined in the decree. Their study covered 52 company-years of dividend action (13 companies for four years). They claimed that they "checked but found very little evidence" to support the classical influence that determine dividend policies in Nigeria during these periods. They concluded that fear and resentment seem to have taken over from the classical forces.

Very recently, Nwankwo and Agbo (2021) examined the relationship between dividend policy and the performance of firms in Nigeria. It employed the ex post facto research design and Ordinary least squares regression technique for analysis. The secondary data used for the period were obtained from the published financial statements of nine Nigerian firms used as case study for the period 2010-2018. The results of the study suggest that there is negative and non-significant relationship between dividends per share on profit after tax of the selected firms, a positive and non-significant relationship between dividends per share and total sales of the selected firms, and a positive and non-significant relationship between dividends per share and total asset of the selected firms. Hence, this study supports the relevant theories of dividend policy.

Kayode, Olayiwola and Abass (2021) opined that in spite of the surfeit of the availability of the literature on the influence of company income tax on dividend pay-out in Nigeria, particularly after the adoption of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs). This study, therefore examined the influence of company income tax on dividend pay-out, providing evidence from listed consumers' goods firms in Nigeria. To achieve the objective of this study, fifteen (15) listed firms were selected, using judgmental sampling technique. Secondary data, which covered years 2012 to 2019 were

retrieved from audited financial reports of the quoted consumer goods firms. Based on the stationarity properties, these data were analysed using pooled, fixed and random effects of ordinary least square. Finding showed that company income tax does not significantly influence dividend payout of listed consumers' goods firms in Nigeria ($\alpha=0.1578$; $p\text{-value} > 0.05$), on the basis of which the study concluded that company income tax does not significantly influence dividend payout of listed consumers' goods firms in Nigeria. Consequently, it was recommended that in order to improve the performances of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, and put them in a position to pay more dividends, enabling and favourable business climate should be envisaged, engineered and created, as doing this will increase their profitability. To increase company income tax rate would end up being counter-productive

Hansda, Kalpataru, and Sinha (2020) explore the relationship between dividend policy and firm value with respect to financial crisis. The investigation is based on data of 500 companies listed on the BSE for the period 2001 to 2017. The dynamic panel regression with two-step system Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) is applied. The findings show that dividend policy does not affect firm value definitely. However, the study observes that financial crisis impacted the relationship between dividend behaviour and firm value. Furthermore, the higher dividend yield in post crisis period may indicate evidences of signaling hypothesis.

Agwu and Godfrey (2019) investigated the controversy raging between dividend policy and firms' value in Nigeria. They made use of 24 quoted companies selected from 10 sectors of Nigerian economy from firm's annual reports and accounts for the period of 2012 to 2017. The results of the descriptive statistics found that few numbers of companies are paying high dividends, while the rest companies are paying very low or no dividends. The correlation test revealed that leverage firms are likely to pay lower dividends in Nigeria. The researchers fitted the three conventional models of panel data analysis and found earnings exerting positive and significant influence on the firms' value, whereas dividend per share insignificantly impacts firms' value. The researchers are suggesting that firms improve on their operations by managing the resources of their firms effectively and efficiently in order to increase earnings. Measures: Dividend Policy, Firm's Value, Earnings, Dividend per Share, Fixed Effects.

Odum, Odum, Omeziri and Egbunike (2019). examined the impact of dividend payout ratio on the value of firm. The study also examined other factors that affect the value of firm while employing companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange. The factors which were considered to affect the value of the firm in this study include profitability, leverage policy ratio, dividend policy ratio, cash holding and the size of the firm. The study employed Panel Ordinary Least Square Regression

Techniques in analyzing the collated data. The sample in this study is drawn from breweries and beverages companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange between the periods 2007-2016. The results showed that profitability ratio and leverage ratio positively and significantly impact on the value of the firm. This implies that only the variables of Firm Leverage, and Profit after Tax are significant factors that drives firm value in both breweries and beverages companies among listed companies in Nigeria. The study however recommends that corporate managers whose interest is to raise firm value should ensure the maximization of Profit after Tax, and focus on policies that will improve the leverage ratio of the firm.

Ugwu, Onyeka and Okwa (2020) evaluated the dividend policy and corporate financial performance with evidence from selected listed consumer good firms in Nigeria within the period 2015-2019; using dividend pay-out ratio, earnings per share and dividend per share as proxies for dividend policy and return on equity as proxy for financial performance with two control variables; firm size and financial leverage. The study employed correlation and ex-post facto research designs. Descriptive statistics and multiple regressions were used for data analysis. Secondary data were used, which were extracted from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and the Audited Annual Reports of the ten selected listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The results of the study show that dividend pay-out ratio; earnings per share and dividend per share are positively related to return on equity. It also revealed that dividend pay-out ratio and earnings per share were statistically insignificant with the return on equity while dividend per share was statistically significant with return on equity within the period of study.

Ubesie, Emejulu and Iyidiobi (2020) analyzed the relationship between dividend policy and firm's financial characteristics with a particular focus to consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It utilized annual time series secondary data obtained from annual report and financial statements of the selected firms for the period of ten (10) years (2009-2018). Dividend policy was operationalized by Dividend per Share (DPS) and Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) while the financial characteristics considered were Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Earnings per Share (EPS). Ex-post facto research design was adopted while analytical techniques employed were Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Pairwise Granger Causality analysis mechanism. Findings revealed that Dividend per Share (DPS) interacts positively with the selected firm's financial characteristics while there is a negative and insignificant relationship between Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) of the selected firms. A positive relationship was maintained between DPR and EPS for the period. Meanwhile, the link between ROA and DPS

was significant at 5% level. More so, evidence from the pairwise granger causality test revealed that there is no directional relationship between dividend policy and financial performance of consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Onwuka (2019) focused on the impact of corporate taxation on dividend payments of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study was set out to determine if there is any significant relationship between corporate taxation and dividend payments of deposit money banks in Nigeria. In addition, the study sought to determine the relationship between corporate tax and profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. It also sought to examine the relationship between profit, dividend and taxes and to investigate the factors that affect dividend payments particularly in the Nigerian banking sector. The standard multiple regression analyses were applied in testing the hypotheses. On the basis of the empirical analysis of the two hypotheses tested, the researcher found out that profit will bring a positive increase in dividend payments of deposit money banks while corporate taxes will cause a decrease in dividend payments of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Williams and Duro (2017) investigated the impact of dividend policy on performance of quoted companies in a developing economy, using a sample of twenty quoted firms in a developing nation actively operating within 2005 to 2016 in the stock market. The Ordinary least square estimation technique was used for the analysis. Their result shows that there is a significant positive impact of dividend pay-out ratio on return on asset. They also found out that there is a positive relationship between return on equity and dividend per share. They concluded that profit after tax should be considered sensitive in relation to dividend payment. It was on this basis that they recommended that dividend policy issuance should be tied to specific range of profit after tax. A situation whereby profit after tax is below the specified range, there should be no dividend. Also, among their recommendations is that most quoted companies on the stock exchange market should be compelled to always make their dividend policy public annually.

Outside the shores of Nigeria, Farrukh, Irshad, Shams Khakwani., Ishaque, and Ansari (2017) examined the impact of dividend policy on shareholders wealth and firm performance in Pakistan. The variables used in the research are dividend policy, shareholders wealth, and firm performance. Dividend per share and dividend yield is used to measure dividend policy. For shareholders wealth, earning per share and share price are used as proxies. Return on equity is used to measure firm performance. From the regression result, it is found out that dividend policy has positively significant impact on shareholders' wealth and firm performance. This study supported dividend relevance theory, signaling effect theory, bird in hand theory and clientele-effect theory

Hafeez, Shahbaz, Iftikhar and Butt (2018). set out to investigate the relationship between dividend policy and firm performance. Design/methodology-the sample contain on 15 manufacturing companies in the year of 2014 to 2017. time series data were calculated from the financial statement of the selected manufacturing firms. Return on asset (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) were used as dependent variables while dividend payout ratio (DPOR), earning per share (EPS), price earnings ratio (PER) were modeled as independent variables. The study adopted multiple regressions while the data used were extracted from the audited financial statement of the 15 selected manufacturing firms for the study for a period between 2014 and 2017. Findings reveal that all the independent variables have a positive relationship with dependent variables which indicate that they positively influence return on investment.

Akram (2017) examined the impact of dividend payments on the value of firms listed on the Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE). He adapted the residual income approach based on Ohlson's (1995) valuation model. By testing different statistical techniques, fixed effect is applied on panel data for 44 firms listed on ISE for the period 2007-2015, inclusive. The findings show a positive significant relationship between dividend payments and the value of firms. The results tend to support agency cost rather than the signaling hypothesis explanation. Moreover, the study suggests that the dividends irrelevance hypothesis is invalid in the case of firms listed on the (ISE). Measures: Dividend Payment, Residual Income, Value of Firms.

Haslum, Shahid, Sajid and Umair (2013) studied the determinants of dividend policy of Pakistani banking sector using data for 27 foreign and domestic banks operating in Islamic and conventional banking in Pakistan Stock exchange. Using stepwise regression analysis, their findings suggest that liquidity, profitability, last year dividend and ownership structure indicates highly significant relationship with dividend payout of Pakistani banks and that profitability, last year dividend and ownership structure shows positive impact on dividend payout while liquidity shows negative impact on the banking industry and that size, leverage agency cost, growth and risk shows insignificant relationship and have no impact on the dividend payout.

Coming back to Nigeria, Akinleye and Ademiloye (2018) examined the impact of dividend policy on performance of five quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2011-2015 using dividend payout ratio and dividend per share were used as independent variables while return on capital employed was used as dependent variable. Data was obtained from the audited annual report and accounts of the sampled firms and adopted multiple regressions for analysis. Their results show that, DPO and DPS have a negative effect on ROCE. The study also reveals that, DPO and DPS are statistically insignificant with ROCE. They recommended that

management of manufacturing firms in the country should not be misguided by the contribution of dividend policy to improve performance to the point that they will consciously distribute more fractions of their earnings than necessary thereby dampening the future growth prospect and investment diversification of their firms.

Usman and Olorunnisola (2019), studied the Effects of Dividend Policy on Corporate Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria; using purposive random sampling method to select seven out of the sixteen quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria based on the size of their capital. Data were obtained from the audited annual reports of the sampled deposit money banks and Nigerian Stock Exchange over a period of ten years (2009-2018). Panel regression was used, and their study from their result showed that dividend policy has significant effect on corporate performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. They recommended that, managers should improve their working capital and measure them with fair value and also that banks should increase the level of asset capital to improve profitability.

Idewele and Murad (2019), investigated the relationship between financial performance and dividend policy for a sample of fifteen Deposit Money Banks quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange 2009 to 2014. Panel data regression analysis was used as the method of analysis, and the model was estimated using the Pooled Least Squares estimation technique. The study revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between dividend pay-out ratio and financial performance. Their study also on the contrary, reveals that there is a negative and insignificant relationship between dividend yield and financial performance. The study recommends that since there is a positive and significant relationship between dividend pay-out ratio and financial performance, firms should strive to maintain healthy and a stable dividend policy. It is also recommended that since dividend yield is not affected by financial performance, investigations should be made to ascertain other factors that affect dividend yield.

Olarewaju, Migiro and Sibanda (2018) examined the causal relationship between dividend payout, retention policy and financial performance in commercial banks in 30 Sub-Saharan African countries [10]. The study covered 250 commercial banks in the Sub-Saharan African countries for the period of 2006 to 2015. Empirical results of the vector error correction block exogeneity Wald test and Pairwise Granger causality test revealed that only retention policies granger cause performance (ROA), even though both major policies posit a positive relationship with performance (ROA) in the Vector Error Correction Model estimate.

Agilebu (2019) employed descriptive and longitudinal design to examine the effect dividend decision and economic value added of quoted Nigeria manufacturing firms [11]. Secondary data from financial statement of 15 quoted manufacturing firms were used. Result revealed a

75 percent variation from the fixed effect results on economic value added of the manufacturing firms. Beta coefficient of the predictor variables found that dividend yield have negative effect on economic value added while dividend per share, dividend payout ratio and retention ratio have positive and significant effect on economic value added of the quoted manufacturing firms.

Using correlated random effects-Hausman test technique with the aid of E-view statistical package and regression analysis, Ubaka (2017) examined the effect of corporate dividend policy on the firm performance of conglomerate firms listed on the floor of the Nigeria stock exchange [12]. It covered the period from 2012-2016 and a sample of three conglomerate firms collected from a population size of seven listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. The regression result showed that firm size, dividend payout, profit after tax and firm age are not significant in determining performance while corporate governance is significant in determining performance of firms in the conglomerate industry in Nigeria.

Gap in Literature

There is no consensus among the empirical studies reviewed about the nature of influence dividend policy has on the performance of corporate firms. It has been argued that dividend policy of corporate firms influences corporate performance in various industries and it assists firms in maximizing the wealth potential of the shareholders (Yarram (2015), Arko, et al. (2014), Gill, Biger and Tibrewala (2010), Al-Malkawi (2007), Anand (2004) and Olantundun (2000)). These arguments have been countered by researchers in related studies such as (Hussainey et al. (2011)), who argued that dividend policy show inverse relationship with corporate performance. These disagreements among researchers have created a gap, thus warranting further examination of the

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used panel data from the financial statements of the quoted banking firms and also Nigerian stock exchange fact books as well as from other relevant sources. Panel data contain observations of multiple phenomena obtained over multiple time periods across firms or individuals.

Population of the study

The population study consists of all quoted banking firms in Nigeria. The total number of quoted banking firms on the Nigerian stock exchange is twenty-two (NSE, 2020). The study variables include; price-earnings ratio, return on equity, retention ratio, dividend payout ratio, and dividend yield.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study adopts the non-probability (purposive) sampling method and it is based on the judgement of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) which classified banks based on operational scope – regional, national and international banks. Thus, five international banking institutions commonly called The Big Five are chosen. The sample size of this study comprises of five banking firms (First Bank Plc, Zenith Bank Plc, Guarantee Trust Bank Plc, Access Bank Plc and United Bank for Africa Plc) quoted on the floor of the NSE.

Methods of data collection

The study utilizes annual panel secondary data for the variables under analysis spanning through 2011-2022. The secondary data are sourced from various annual reports of the different banking firms sampled in the study.

Model Specification

We express the different feature of corporate performance as a function of corporate dividend policy.

$$\text{Financial Performance} = f(\text{Dividend Policy}) \quad (3.1)$$

The econometric form of the model is stated as:

$$\text{MPS}_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{DPR}_{t1} + \alpha_2 \text{ERR}_{t2} + \alpha_3 \text{DIY}_{t3} + \mu_t \quad (3.2)$$

Where;

MPS = Market Price per Share

DPR = Dividend Payout Ratio

ERR = Earnings Retention Ratio

DIY = Dividend Yield

α_1 , α_2 , and α_3 = Constant parameters

α_0 = Intercept

t = different firm I in year t .

μ_t = Error term

α_1 , α_2 , and $\alpha_3 > 0$

Operational Measures of Variables

Market Price per Share (MPS): this is the ratio for valuing a company that measures its market price of share. This index determines the worth of a company's share in the market as perceived by investors. Firm's dividend policy can either affect it positively or negatively. A liberal dividend policy of a firm has the capacity of triggering the upward swing in the market price of a firm.

Independent Variables

An independent variable which is sometimes referred to as the explanatory variable is any factor that can affect the response or dependent variable. In this analysis,

retention ratio (DRR), dividend yield (DIY), and dividend payout ratio (DPR) are the explanatory variables in the model.

Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR): this refers to the ratio of total amount of dividends paid out to shareholders relative to the net income of the company. It is the percentage of earnings paid to shareholders in dividends. Dividend payout ratio has a strong effect on market price per share of firms such that the higher the dividend payout ratio, the high the market price per share of the firm. This is attributed to the fact that investors and analysts see it as a less risky firm compare to firms with lower dividend payout ratio. We therefore expect a positive relationship between the dividend payout ratio (DPR) and market price per share (MPS). That is $\alpha_1 > 0$.

Dividend Yield (DIY): this refers to the ratio of annual dividends per share to market price per share of a firm. It is the ratio of total dividends paid out to shareholders relative to the net income of the firm. The higher the dividend yield, the higher the market price per share since investors and analysts see it a profitable firm with prospective future for growth. We therefore expect a positive relationship between the dividend yield (DIY) and market price per share (MPS). That is $\alpha_2 > 0$.

Earnings Retention Ratio (ERR): this is the proportion of earnings kept back in the business as retained earnings. It is the percentage of net income that is retained to grow the business, rather than being paid as dividends. The higher the retention ratio, the lower the market price per share of the firm. This is as a result of the perceived risk associated with firms that have a high retention ratio. Therefore, it is expected that the relationship between retention ratio and market price per share (MPS) is negative. $\alpha_3 < 0$.

3.7 Data Analysis Technique The techniques for data analyses are descriptive statistics and Panel Ordinary Least Square (OLS) techniques to examine the effect of dividend policy on the value of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Fixed Effect

Two panel regression analysis (Fixed and Random Effect) was carried out to establish the possible effect in each model. Based on Borenstein, Hedges, Higgins and Rothstein (2021), the fixed effect analysis assumes that the true effect size is the same in all selected country, and the only reason for effect size varies between countries will be sampling error (error in estimating the effect size). Thus, the summary effect is the main estimate of this common effect size. Fixed effects estimates have been used to correct for the problems such as omitted variable bias that may arise from pure cross section regressions. The fixed effects model takes account of the unobservable country specific effects which are assumed to be fixed parameters to be estimated.

Random Effect

However, in the random effects analysis, it is assumed that the true effect size varies from one country to the other, and that the countries in the analysis represent a random sample of effect sizes that could have been observed (Borenstein et. al. 2021). Thus, under the random effects model the goal is not to estimate one true effect, but to estimate the mean of a distribution of effects.

Hausman Test

In order to choose the best methodology for solving the problem of unobserved effects, we therefore apply the Hausman (Hausman, 1978) test. Thus, the choice between fixed and random effect models was done using the Hausman model selection criteria. The Hausman selection test is based on the fact that the individual effects and the regressors are uncorrelated. In such circumstance, the random effects model becomes the focus of the interpretation; however, the fixed effect was showcased for empirical robustness. On the other hand, the fixed effect model was the focus of analyses of the study.

Decision Rule

Using the Hausman test: the basic idea of this test is to examine whether we can accept the null hypothesis, which means that random effects is the best solution, and if we reject it, fixed effects estimation will be the most appropriate model. The making decision, when the P-value of the Hausman test is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude the fixed effects is the most appropriate and if otherwise, the random effects model will be the most appropriate for the study.

The E-views statistical software automatically determines the above listed test, and was used basically for decision making for the research work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The annual data for all the variables employed in this study is presented in the table below;

Data Presentation

The data presented below shows the Market Price per Share, Dividend per Share, Dividend yield and Earnings Retention Ratio of selected deposit money banks from 2011 to 2022.

Data Analysis

In this section, the results from the test of the hypotheses

Table 4.1: Market Price per Share, Dividend per Share, Dividend yield and Earnings Retention Ratio of selected deposit money banks from 2011 to 2022.

C_ID	YEAR	COMPANY	MPS	DPR	DIY	ERR
1	2011	ACCESS	5.02	34.89933	10.35857	65.10067
1	2012	ACCESS	9.02	39.47368	6.651885	60.52632
1	2013	ACCESS	9.25	37.97468	6.486486	62.02532
1	2014	ACCESS	6.66	31.74603	9.009009	68.25397
1	2015	ACCESS	4.6	20	11.52174	80
1	2016	ACCESS	5.5	22.08835	10	77.91165
1	2017	ACCESS	10.47	29.3578	6.112703	70.6422
1	2018	ACCESS	6.8	28.29268	8.529412	71.70732
1	2019	ACCESS	10	24.26582	7.25648	75.73418
1	2020	ACCESS	10	35.26523	9.26512	64.73477
1	2021	ACCESS	9.30	30.26563	6.56256	69.73437
1	2022	ACCESS	10.40	36.23654	11.55023	63.76346
2	2011	FBN	9.84	33.72632	6.097561	66.26316
2	2012	FBN	15.6	33.75527	5.128205	66.24473
2	2013	FBN	16.1	46.2963	6.21118	53.7037
2	2014	FBN	8.5	46.80851	12.94118	53.19149
2	2015	FBN	4.7	23.25581	2.12766	76.74419
2	2016	FBN	3.21	38.46154	4.672897	61.53846
2	2017	FBN	8.99	17.3913	2.224694	82.6087
2	2018	FBN	7.95	15.15152	3.144654	84.84848
2	2019	FBN	6.15	19.25642	5.25452	80.74358
2	2020	FBN	9.21	18.56745	7.36524	81.43255
2	2021	FBN	14.02	31.02564	16.25862	68.97436
2	2022	FBN	10.90	21.25466	15.23542	78.74534
3	2011	GTB	13.84	50.29586	6.141618	49.70414
3	2012	GTB	22.49	42.62295	5.780347	57.37705
3	2013	GTB	26.96	45.74132	5.378338	54.25868
3	2014	GTB	23.36	43.22767	6.421233	56.77233
3	2015	GTB	20	43.42857	7.6	56.57143
3	2016	GTB	23	37.47323	7.608696	62.52677
3	2017	GTB	40.53	45	6.661732	55
3	2018	GTB	34.45	42.30769	7.982583	57.69231
3	2019	GTB	29.7	44.26522	6.8652	55.73478
3	2020	GTB	32.7	41.23565	7.563255	58.76435
3	2021	GTB	26	45.12535	6.532533	54.87465
3	2022	GTB	23	40.26533	6.32565	59.73467
4	2011	UBA	2.1	0	23.80952	100
4	2012	UBA	4.56	30.12048	10.96491	69.87952
4	2013	UBA	7.93	32.89474	6.30517	67.10526

Table 4.1. Contd.

4	2014	UBA	4.15	6.410256	2.409639	93.58974
4	2015	UBA	3.52	31.91489	17.04545	68.08511
4	2016	UBA	4.32	29.25532	12.73148	70.74468
4	2017	UBA	10.3	38.81279	8.252427	61.18721
4	2018	UBA	7.7	38.63636	11.03896	61.36364
4	2019	UBA	7.15	38.54256	9.65282	61.45744
4	2020	UBA	7.88	21.23568	12.80355	78.76432
4	2021	UBA	8.05	35.23533	7.132562	64.76467
4	2022	UBA	7.60	22.32566	11.85323	77.67434
5	2011	ZENITH	12.01	67.85714	7.910075	32.14286
5	2012	ZENITH	18.11	50.15674	8.834898	49.84326
5	2013	ZENITH	22.9	58.13953	7.641921	41.86047
5	2014	ZENITH	17.98	55.37975	9.733037	44.62025
5	2015	ZENITH	18.83	59.52381	10.62135	40.47619
5	2016	ZENITH	14.35	49.02913	14.07666	50.97087
5	2017	ZENITH	25.5	48.82459	10.58824	51.17541
5	2018	ZENITH	23.05	45.52846	12.14751	54.47154
5	2019	ZENITH	18.6	38.25625	11.25452	61.74375
5	2020	ZENITH	28.60	42.82465	15.4	57.17535
5	2021	ZENITH	25.15	43.23523	12.5	56.76477
5	2022	ZENITH	24.00	43.30000	13.3	56.70000

SOURCE: annual reports of sampled quoted deposit money banks and the daily official lists of the NSE for the period 2011- 2022

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics.

	MPS	DPR	DIY	ERR
Mean	13.46111	34.91408	8.426381	65.08592
Median	10.00000	38.54256	7.641921	61.45744
Maximum	40.53000	35.22632	23.80952	256.2500
Minimum	2.100000	0.00000	2.127660	-5.263158
Std. Dev.	9.103932	33.23390	3.946133	33.23390
Skewness	0.977014	-4.127931	1.381981	4.127931
Kurtosis	3.360177	25.97630	6.679858	25.97630
Jarque-Bera	7.402417	1117.631	39.71407	1117.631
Probability	0.024694	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	605.7500	1571.134	379.1872	2928.866
Sum Sq. Dev.	3646.790	48597.64	685.1666	48597.64
Observations	60	60	60	60

SOURCE: Author's computations using E-views 10

carried out and its interpretation is presented. Data for this research was analyzed using the Econometric Views (E-Views) version 9 statistical application packages.

Analysis of the Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.2 provides the descriptive account of the five quoted deposit money banks used in this study over the period 2011 - 2022. The descriptive results in Table 4.2 revealed mean values of 13.46, 34.91, 8.43 and 65.09 for

market price per share, dividend payout ratio, dividend yield and earnings retention ratio respectively. The mean value of 34.91 implies that on the average, quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria declared about 35 per cent dividends during the period under review. The figure is relatively high, suggesting that shareholdings of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria is attractive, and shareholders are getting value for money.

The minimum value of 0.00 for DPR is an indication that a bank did not declare dividend in a particular year

Table 4.2: Results of Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test				
Equation: Untitled				
Test cross-section random effects				
Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		2.187897	2	0.0009
Cross-section random effects test comparisons:				
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
DPR	0.018908	0.022483	0.000008	0.0095
DIY	-0.075295	-0.071848	0.001271	0.0030
ERR	0.562222	0.236532	0.251555	0.0002

SOURCE: Author's computations using E-views 10

TABLE 4.3: Estimates of $MPS_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1DPR_t + \alpha_2DIY_t + \alpha_3ERR_t + \Theta_t$
Fixed Effects Panel Regression Results

Dependent Variable: MPS				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 09/26/24 Time: 18:28				
Sample: 2011 2022				
Periods included: 12				
Cross-sections included: 5				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 60				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	13.43544	2.840346	4.730210	0.0000
DPR	2.864737	2.344980	3.055350	0.0001
DIY	0.278157	0.115172	2.415152	0.0031
ERR	-0.939197	0.072170	-5.954250	0.0169
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.757285	Mean dependent var		13.46111
Adjusted R-squared	0.718962	S.D. dependent var		9.103932
S.E. of regression	4.826270	Akaike info criterion		6.128060
Sum squared resid	885.1295	Schwarz criterion		6.409096
Log likelihood	-130.8813	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.232827
F-statistic	19.76040	Durbin-Watson stat		1.862943
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

SOURCE: Author's computations using E-views 9

during the period of study. Similarly, the maximum value of 35.26 for DPR suggests that a bank declared a dividend in a particular year that is little above 35 percent of the earnings. The median value of 38.54 connotes that

more than 50 per cent of the deposit money banks utilized in this study declared little above 38 percent of their earnings as dividend per share in a particular year during the period under consideration. Additionally, the

mean value of 65.08 for retained earnings is high, implying low dividend payout ratio. Although, low payout ratio suggests that the banks are pursuing growth, shareholders may prefer immediate payments of dividends because of the level of uncertainty inherent in future earnings.

Furthermore, the average MPS of ₦13.46 signifies that the market price per share is high in relative to book value of 50 kobo per share; this further confirmed that investment in shares of banks in Nigeria is worthwhile and profitable. The descriptive results in Table 4.2 revealed that the standard deviations of the 9 variables are lower than their respective means, suggesting that the variables do not vary greatly from each other, and may be normally distributed. The coefficients of variation are lower than 5 percent in all the 3 variables, confirmed this position.

Presentation of Empirical Results

Market price per share (MPS) was regressed on DPR, DIY and ERR using pooled regression, fixed effect or LSDV model and random effect model. The three models were statistically significant, implying that the models can be used to draw valid conclusions and policy implications. This is confirmed by their respective F-values which were significant at 5 percent level. Since the 3 models: POLS, FEM and REM are statistically significant, there is need to carry out test for best model selection.

Table 4.3 presents the results of the Hausman test for best model selection between Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (POLS) and Fixed Effects Models. The decision rule is that if the probability value is less than 5 percent, fixed effect model is selected otherwise, it is rejected. The results of Hausman Test in Table 4 favoured the selection of Fixed Effects model over the Random Effects model. On this basis, this study will carry out its analysis, draw conclusion and make recommendations using the fixed effect model.

Thus, the table below presents Fixed-effects, using 60 observations

Analysis of Empirical Results

Table 4.3 shows the relationship between dividend policy and the value of select quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the regression results in revealed that DPR has a significant positive effect on MPS of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period 2011 – 2022. This is confirmed by the t-statistics ratio of 3.055350, which is significant at 5 per level of significance (p-value of 0.0001 is less than 0.05 level of significance). The DPS coefficient of 2.864737 signifies that a 1 per cent increase in DPR will result in about 2.86 per cent increase in MPS. The results imply that increase in the amount of dividends declaration by the management of deposit money banks in Nigeria will lead

to market stock price appreciation.

Similarly, ERR has a significant negative effect on MPS at 5 per cent level of significance (p-value of 0.0169 is less than 0.05 level of significance). This position is confirmed by the significant negative t-ratio of -5.9545. The coefficient of -0.939197 for RPS connotes that a 1 per cent increase in RPS will bring about 94 per cent decline in MPS. In other words, increase in ERR implies decrease in dividend payout and consequently, fall in MPS. The implication is that for the management of quoted deposit money banks to experience appreciation in MPS, they must increase their dividend payout ratio and reduce the retention ratio.

Also, the coefficient of dividend yield is 0.278157 and its associated p-value is 0.0031. This indicated that the relationship between dividend yield and market price per share is also positive and statistically significant. A 1% increase in dividend yield would cause market price per share to decrease by approximately 0.278157%.

These findings lend support to the bird-in-the-hand argument that stockholders will prefer present dividends, and stocks paying more dividends will command a higher stock price. Again, the findings are contrary to the notion that low payout ratio may lead to increase in stock price. Furthermore, the regression results also revealed that DPR, DIY and ERR altogether explained the variation in MPS. This revelation is confirmed by the F-value of 19.76040, which is significant at 5 per cent level as shown by the P-value (F). The significant F-value is also a testimony that the model is reliable and can be used to draw valid conclusions. The adjusted R-squared of 0.718962 suggests that about 72 per cent of the variation in the market price per share (MPS) is jointly accounted for by DPR, DIY and ERR, while the remaining 28 per cent is due to other factors not captured in this study. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson value of approximately 2 (1.862943) shows that the model is free from first order autocorrelation.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Dividend payout ratio is a main attribute of dividend policy such that its increase triggers the performance of firm's value as measured by market price per share. Thus, 1 per cent increase in DPR will result in about 2.86 per cent increase in MPS. This is consistent with Anandasayanan and Velnampy (2016); Rachid and Wiame (2016); Dada et al. (2015); Eyigege (2015); and Abdul, and Muhibudeen (2015) that dividend payout ratio of firms promotes firms value positively. However, contrarily to the findings of Fodio (2009); Nazir et al. (2010); Hussainey et al. (2011); and Baskin (1989) that dividend payout of firms hinders growth value.

Dividend yield is also positive and significant with price-earnings ratio. This is in contrast to the findings of Fodio (2009); Nazir et al. (2010); and Hussainey et al. (2011)

that discover a negative relationship between dividend yield and firms' value but in consistency with the works of Anandasayanan and Velnampy (2016); Rachid and Wiame (2016); Dada et al. (2015) that affirms a positive relationship between dividend yield and market price of firms. This is attributed to the high level of risk perceived by investors and analysts from banking firms that face low dividend yield. As a result of their low dividend yield and inherent perceived risk, the price-earnings ratio of banking firms continues to dwindle from the expected.

Retention ratio is negative and significant with price-earnings ratio. This is synonymous with Rachid and Wiame (2016); Dada et al. (2015); and Abdul, and Muhibudeen (2015) that retention ratio of firms influences firms value. However, contrarily to the findings of Nazir et al. (2010); Hussainey et al. (2011); and Baskin (1989) that retention ratio of firms hinders firms' growth value. This is attributed to the fact that most of the projects funded through retained earnings by banking firms improve their values; and consequently, market price in the long-run.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of dividend policy on the stock price of 5 quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria, for the period of 12 years, spanning from 2011 - 2022. Data was utilized from the annual reports of selected banks and the daily official lists of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) over the period of study. Descriptive statistics and panel data regression in the form of Fixed Effects Model (FEM) was adopted as the methods of estimation. The regression results reveal that dividend payout ratio (DPR) and Dividend yield (DIY) have significant positive effect on the stock price, while Earnings retention ratio (ERR) has a significant negative effect on the stock price of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Dividend payout ratio (DPR) has a significant positive effect on the stock price. In other words, increase in the amount of dividend declaration is positively associated with rise in stock price. Investors may view continued dividend declaration by banks as indication of being healthy. Thus, may find such banks attractive and be willing to invest in their stocks, thereby, resulting to stock price appreciation.
2. Earnings retention ratio (ERR) has a significant negative effect on the stock price. Increase in the amount of earnings retained by banks will result to decline or fall in stock price. This is because stockholders prefer present dividends to future dividends.
3. Dividend payments and retained earnings are important determinants of stock price in the Nigeria banking industry. Stock price appreciation can be enhanced

through steady dividends payments and low retention ratio.

4. It is also concluded that the stock price of quoted deposit money banks is over-valued, and investment in their stocks is worthwhile and will offer value for money. Based on the conclusions of the study, we make the following recommendations:

1. Board of directors of quoted deposit money banks should declare dividends out of the earnings, no matter how little, as doing so will lead to increase in share price.
2. Board of directors of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria should adopt a policy of high dividend payout ratio in order to attract increase in stock price.
3. Management of quoted deposit money banks, financial analysts, stock brokers, shareholders and investing public among others should consider dividends and retained earnings decisions in predicting the market price of shares for quoted banks in Nigeria.
4. The study also recommends that investors should invest in the shares of quoted banks in Nigeria, as doing so will offer them fair return on investment and value for money.

REFERENCES

- Abor, J., & Bokpin, G. A. (2019). Investment opportunities, corporate finance, and dividend payout policy: Evidence from emerging markets. *Studies in economics and finance*.
- Adefila, J. J., Oladipo, J. A., & Adeoti, J. O. (2013). The effect of dividend policy on the market price of shares in Nigeria: Case study of fifteen quoted companies. *International Journal of Accounting*, 2(1), 78-89
- Adelegan, O. (2003). An empirical analysis of the relationship between cash flow and dividend changes in Nigeria. *African Development Review*, 15(1), 35-49
- Adelegan, O. J. (2002). The pecking order hypothesis and corporate dividend pay-out: Nigerian evidence. *African Review of Money, Finance and Banking, Supplementary issues of Savings and Development*, 75-94
- Adelegan, O. J., & Inanga, E. (2001). A contextual analysis of the determinants of dividend patterns of commercial banks in Nigeria. A paper presented at the 24th annual European accounting association congress in Athens, Greece.
- Aivazian, V., Booth, L., & Cleary, S. (2003). Do emerging market firms follow different dividend policies from U.S firms? *The Journal of Financial Research*, 26(3): 371-387.
- Ajanthan, A. (2013) The relationship between dividend payout and firm profitability: A study of listed hotels and restaurant companies in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(6), June 2013.
- Akinsulire, O. I. (2019). *Financial management* (5th Edition). Ceemol Nigeria Limited
- Ali, A. (2007). Dividend policy and payout ratio: Evidence from Kuala Lumpur stock exchange. *Journal of Risk Finance*, 8(4), 349-363
- Al-Malkawi, H., Rafferty, M., Pillai, R. (2018), Dividend policy: A review of theories and empirical evidence. *International Bulletin of Business Administration*, 9(9), 171-200.
- Amidu, M. (2007). How does dividend policy affect performance of the firm on Ghana stock exchange? *Invest, Manag, Financ. Innov.* 4(2), 104-112
- Anand, M. (2004). Factors influencing dividend policy decisions of corporate India. *ICFAI Journal of Applied Finance*, 10(2), 5-16.

- Anandasayanan S., & Velnampy, T. (2016). Dividend policy and corporate profitability: Econometric analysis of listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Commerce and Management Research*, 2(1) 53-58.
- Asamoah, G. N. (2010). The impact of dividend announcement on share price behaviour in Ghana. *Journal of Business and Economics Research*, 8(4), 47-60.
- Asika (1991) The effect of dividend policy on the market price of shares. Case study of five quoted companies. *International Journal of accounting*, 2(1) 78-89.
- Autio, E., Rannikko, H., Handelberg, J., & Kiuru, P. (2021). Analyses on the Finnish high-growth entrepreneurship ecosystem.
- Baker, H. K., Singleton, J. C., & Veit, E. T. (2011). Survey research in corporate finance. *Oxford University Press*
- Baridam (2008). An assessment of the determinants of a study of selected listed firms share price in Nigeria.
- Baskin, (1989). An Empirical Study of Dividend Policy of Quoted Companies in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1), 85-101
- Bekaert, Jr. H. (2018). *Increasing shareholder value: Distribution policy, a corporate challenge*. Boston: Klinwer Academic Publishers.
- Black, F. & Scholes, M. (1973). The Pricing of Options and Corporate Liabilities, *Journal of Political Economics*. 81(3), 637-654
- Booth, C. (2000). *Dividend policy in the introduction to corporate finance* (2nd edition). John Wiley & Sons Publishing.
- Borenstein, M., Hedges, L. V., Higgins, J. P., & Rothstein, H. R. (2021). *Introduction to meta-analysis*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Brockman, P., & Unlu, E. (2009). Dividend policy, creditor rights, and the agency cost of debt. *Finance Department Faculty Publications Central Bank of Nigeria* (2018), Statistical Bulletin, Abuja.
- DeAngelo (2006). Dividend policy and its impact on stock price: A study on commercial banks listed in Dhaka stock exchange. *Global Disclosure of Economics and Business*, 3(1),44-54.
- Eyigege, A. I. (2015). Dividend payout of manufacturing firms quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange and its impact on financial performance. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Management*, 1(9). 60-86
- Farsio, F., Geary, A., & Moser, J. (2004). The relationship between dividends and earnings. *Journal for economic educators*, 4(4), 1-5.
- Farrukh, K., Irshad, S., Shams Khakwani, M., Ishaque, S., & Ansari, N. Y. (2017). Impact of dividend policy on shareholders wealth and firm performance in Pakistan. *Cogent Business & Management*, 4(1), 1408208.
- Faure, A. P. (2017). *Investment: An introduction*. Quoin Institute (Pty) Limited and bookboon.
- Fodio, M. I. (2009). The dividend policy of firms quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange: An empirical analysis. *African Journal of Business Management*, 3(10), 555-566
- Glen, J. D., Karmokolias, Y., Miller, R. R. & Shah, S. (2005). Dividend policy and behaviour in emerging markets: To pay or not to pay, IFC discussion paper series No 26, *The World Bank and International Finance Corporation*.
- Gordon, M. J. (1959). Dividends, earnings and stock prices. *Review of Economic Stat.* 41, 99-105
- Gugler, K. (2017). Corporate governance, dividend payout policy and the interrelation between dividends, R&D and capital investment. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 27(2003), 1297-1321
- Hafeez, M. M., Shahbaz, S., Iftikhar, I., & Butt, H. A. (2018). Impact of dividend policy on firm performance. *International Journal of Advanced Study and Research Work*, 1(4), 1-5.
- Hussainey et al., (2001). Dividend policy and share price volatility: UK evidence on market price of shares. *Journal of Risk Finance and Finance*, 12(1), 57-68
- Izedonmi, O. I. F., & Eriki, P. (1996). Determinants of dividend policy in emerging markets: Evidence from MENA stock markets. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 37(2016), 283-289.
- Jabbouri, I. (2021). Determinants of corporate dividend policy in emerging markets: Evidence from MENA stock markets. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 37, 283-298.
- Jensen, G. R., Solberg, D. P. & Zom, T.S. (1992). Simultaneous determination of insider ownership, debt, and dividend policies. *Journal of Finance and Quantitative Analysis*, 27(2), 247-263.
- John, K. & Nachman, C. (1985). Risky debt, investment incentives, and reputation in a sequential equilibrium. *Journal of Finance*, 40, 863-878
- Kayode, A. A., Olayiwola, R. L., & Abass, B. O. (2021) Influence of company income tax on dividend pay-out: evidence from listed consumers' goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*. 2(4), 625-633
- Kazmierska-Jozwiak, B. (2015). Determinants of dividend policy: Evidence from polish listed companies. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23(2015), 473-477
- Kehinde, A. (2001). Determinants of dividend payout ratio: Evidence from Karachi stock exchange (KSE). *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business Research*, 1(1), 20-27.
- La Porta et al (2000). Agency problems and dividend policies around the world. *Journal of Finance*, (55), 1-33.
- Lagoarde-Segot, T., (2020). Does stock market development always improve firm level financing? Evidence from Tunisia. *Research in International Business Finance*, 27, 183-208
- Lintner, J. (1956). Distribution of incomes of corporation among dividends, retained earnings and taxes. *American Economic Review*, 3, 97-113
- Macheshwari, T. (2003). Dividends, earnings, and stock prices. *Review of Economic studies*, 41, 99-105
- Modigliani, F., & Miller, M. H. (1961). Dividend policy, growth, and the valuation of shares. *Journal of Business*, 34, 411-433
- Musa, I. F. (2009). The dividend policy of firms quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange: An Empirical Analysis. *African Journal of Business Management*, 3(10), 555-566
- Nachmais (1976). International research journal of finance and economics. *Euro Journals Publishing Inc* 43(78-84)
- Nazir et al., (2010). The determinants of corporate dividend policy. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 8 (3), 17-28
- Nini, G, Smith, D., & Sufi, A. (2007). Creditor control rights and firm investment policy. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 92(3), 400-420
- Nnadi, M. A., & Akomi, M. E. (2008). The effect of tax on dividend policy of banks. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 19, 48-55.
- Nnadi, M. A., Wogboroma, N., & Kabel, B. (2013). Determinants of dividend policy: Evidenced from listed firms in the African stock exchanges. *PANOECOMICUS*, 6, 725-741
- Nwankwo, S. N. P., & Agbo, E. I. (2021). Examination of the relationship between dividend policy and firm performance in nigeria. *GE-International Journal of Management Research*, 9(5), 22-42.
- Nwosu, G. (2008). Determinant of dividend payout of quoted companies in Nigerian stock exchange. *Journal of economic and finance* 3(2), 211-224
- Nwude, C. E. (2020). The basic principles of financial management. 1st edition. *Enugu: ChukeNwude Nigeria*.
- Odedokun, M. O (1995). Dividend policy, investment spending and financing decisions: Evidence from Nigerian quoted non-financial firms. *Nigerian Journal of Economics and Social Studies*, 37(3), 185-202
- Odesa, J. O. & Ekezie, A. (2015). Determinants of dividend policy in quoted companies in Nigeria. *Communication Panorama African and Global Perspective* 1(1), Sept-Oct
- Odum, A. N., Odum, C. G., Omeziri, R. I., & Egbunike, C. F. (2019). Impact of dividend payout ratio on the value of firm: A study of companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. *Indonesian Journal of Contemporary Management Research*, 1(1), 25-34.
- Olamide, O., & Adewunmi, W. (1987) Determinants of dividend policy in quoted companies in Nigeria. *Communication Panorama African and Global Perspective* 1(1), 1-13
- Oyejide, T. A. (1976). Company dividend policy in Nigeria: An empirical analysis. *Nigerian Journal of Economics and Social Studies*, 18(2), July, 179-195
- Pandey (1999). *Financial Management* (9th Eds). Vikas Publishing House Pvt Limited
- Porterfield, J. T. S. (1965). *Investment decisions and capital costs*. Englewood, Cliffs: Prentice-Hall
- Rachid M., & Wiame, B (2016). The relationship between dividend payments and firm performance: A study of listed companies in Morocco. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(4), 469-482

- Ramadan, E. (2013). Mediating effect of liquidity on firm performance and dividend payout of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Economic Development, Management, IT, Finance and Marketing*, 8(1), 15-35.
- Rely, F. K. & Brown, K. C. (2019). *Investment analysis and portfolio management* (10th Edition). South-Western Cengage Learning
- Rufus, A., & Soyoye I. (2014) Determinants of dividend payout in the Nigerian banking industry. *Proceedings of 9th Annual London Business Research Conference 4-5, August 2014, Imperial College, London, UK.*
- Saunders ET. Al. (1997) Dividend policy and corporate profitability. Econometric analysis of listed manufacturing firm. *International journal of commerce and management research*, 2(3), 1-19.
- Shefrin, S. (1984). The impact of dividend policy on the share price volatility: Malaysian construction and material companies. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(5), 1-8.
- Sheh, H, S. (2011). Effects of dividend announcement on shareholders' value: evidence from Dhaka stock exchange. *Journal of Business Research*, 7(1), 61-72.
- Shukla, R. (2011). Why do firms pay dividends? international evidence on the determinants of dividend policy. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 89 (1), 62-82
- Soyode, A (1975). Dividend policy in an era of indigenization: A comment. *Nigerian Journal of Economics and Social Studies*, 17(8), 126
- Suleman et al. (2011). Relationship between Free cash flow and dividend: Moderating role of firm size. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(5), 16-23.
- Ubesie, M. C., Emejulu, C. E., & Iyidiobi, F. C. (2020). Effect of dividend policy on financial performance of consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Science Journal of Business and Management*, 13(1), 7-15.
- Ugwu, C. C., Onyeka, V. N., & Okwa, I. E. (2020). Dividend policy and corporate financial performance: evidence from selected listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 3(3).
- Uwalomwa, U., Jimoh, J., & Anijesusbola, A. (2012). Dividend policy and firm performance: A study of listed firms in Nigeria. *Accounting and Management Information Systems*, 11(3), 442-454
- Yegon, C., Cheruiyot, J., Sang, J., Cheruiyot, P. K., Kirui, J., & Rotich, J. (2014). Effects of dividend policy on firm's financial performance: Econometric analysis of listed manufacturing firms in Kenya. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(12), 136-144.